

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style and guidelines:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t ha) or with small-scale studies in grams per pot (g pot) or grams per row (g row)
- Define in footnotes of legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N ha; not 60 kg ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out in full the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were . . . or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in . . .
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or some numbers higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common – not trade – names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should have quantified data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

A new rice form with low endogenous gibberellin content

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AURRI has developed a rice mutant called Alexeenko from the traditional variety Krasnodarsky 424 by chemical

mutagenesis. Alexeenko is an ultradwarf that is less than 25 cm tall at maturity and has 10-cm-long panicles (Fig. 1).

The physiological and biochemical properties of fifth-generation mutant plants (M_5) were compared with those of Krasnodarsky 424. To determine the endogenous gibberellins, the rice plants were grown in water culture without gibberellic acid (GA) and with 0.001% GA until 2-leaf stage (Fig. 2) and the

1. Alexeenko, an ultradwarf mutants.

2. Krasnodarsky (1) and Alexeenko (3) without gibberellic acid, compared with Krasnodarsky (2) and Alexeenko (4) treated with 0.001% gibberellic acid. Alexeenko showed 6 times more reaction.

Reaction of Alexeenko and Krasnodarsky to exogenous gibberellic acid.

	Krasnodarsky 424	Krasnodarsky 424 + GA (0.001%)	Alexeenko	Alexeenko + GA (0.001%)
RNA, seedling leaves (mg/g fresh matter)	5.693	5.399	6.485	4.470
DNA, seedling leaves (mg/g fresh matter)	1.047	1.072	0.968	0.860
RNA/DNA, leaves	5.4	5.0	6.7	5.2
RNA, seedling roots (mg/g fresh matter)	6.417	9.313	4.612	7.375
DNA, seedling roots (mg/g fresh matter)	0.969	1.674	0.647	1.028
RNA/DNA, roots	6.6	5.6	7.1	7.2
Protein, seedling leaves (% of fresh matter)	6.4	5.2	7.1	4.3
Protein, seedling roots (% of fresh matter)	6.2	5.6	4.4	7.4
Chlorophyll, seedling leaves (mg/g fresh matter)	1.8	0.9	1.6	1.0
Carotenoids, seedling leaves (mg/g fresh matter)	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.3
Silica, mature plant straw (% of dry matter)	6.0		20.0	

length of the first real leaf sheath was measured.

Alexeenko had six times more reaction to exogenous GA than Krasnodarsky 424 (Fig. 2), perhaps because of the possible transformation of endogenous gibberellins biosynthesis genes which may have decreased gene activity. This transformation also changed plant morphology, nucleic acid and protein metabolism, pigment content, and silica content of straw from mature plants (see table).

Alexeenko will be used in breeding semidwarf rice varieties. □

Individuals, organizations, and media who wish additional details of information presented in IRRN should write directly to the author.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Field screening for sheath blight and rice root nematode resistance

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Ten rice varieties were field screened for resistance to sheath blight (ShB) (*Rhizoctonia solani*) and rice root nematode (*Hirschmanniella oryzae* Soltwedel, Luc and Goodey) at the State Seed Farm, Adoor, Kerala, where both problems are common. It was observed that high nematode incidence encourages severe ShB infection.

Table 1. Reaction of rice varieties to sheath blight.

Variety	Hill infection (%)	Disease index
Bharati	57	1.34
Rohini	60	1.77
Sabari	58	2.04
CO 25	69	2.77
IR8	70	3.27
Annapurna	73	3.29
Jaya	74	3.37
Triveni	72	4.56
PTB12	77	5.06
Jyothi	78	6.73
CD	1.371	0.536

Table 2. Population of rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* in roots of different rice varieties.

Variety	Nematodes/10-g root sample	
	Healthy plants	Diseased plants
PTB12	3.45	4.19
Annapurna	2.83	4.28
Triveni	4.04	4.32
Jaya	3.50	5.03
Bharati	3.81	5.37
Sabari	3.44	5.55
Rohini	4.98	5.65
CO 25	4.56	5.81
IR8	4.18	6.08
Jyothi	3.46	6.22
CD	0.445	0.853

Disease intensity and percent hill infection were recorded for both problems, using standard methods.

Bharati and Rohini had significantly lower levels of disease intensity, followed by Sabari, CO 25, IR8, Annapurna, and Jaya (Table 1). Maximum disease intensity was recorded for Triveni, PTB12, and Jyothi. Bharati, Sabari, and Rohini also had significantly lower hill infection. All varieties were susceptible to rice root nematode (Table 2). Roots of plants with ShB had

significantly more nematodes than roots of healthy plants (Table 2).

Trials conducted at IRRI indicate only a few rice varieties have ShB resistance. In Kerala, not one of 36 evaluated have ShB resistance. □

Leaf scald disease of rice at Ponnampet, Karnataka, India

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Ponnampet is a high-elevation area near the Malnad Mountains of India. Rice cultivation is intensive and blast disease is a serious problem. During 1982 kharif, leaf scald (LSc) (caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae*) incidence was higher than normal in experimental plots and farmers' fields.

We tested 20 rice cultivars for resistance to LSc at the Agricultural Research Station, Ponnampet, during 1982 kharif. Plot size was 1.2 × 4.5 m and cultivars were planted at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Intan and BKB were resistant checks and Cauvery and Tellahamsa were